

Evaluation of National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) as Perceived by Unity School Teachers in Anambra State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the evaluation of the quality of healthcare services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) as perceived by Unity School teachers in Anambra state. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The study utilised Test-retest for the validation of the instrument which was a questionnaire. Twenty (20) teachers Police Children School ii, Awka where used for the test-retest. The total number of male and female unity school teachers in Anambra state came up to three hundred and fifty one (351). Three hundred and twenty nine (329) teachers took part in this study by responding to the questionnaire. Data collected where analysed using mean scores for the research questions and T-test was used for testing the hypothesis. Major findings reveal that unity school teachers in Anambra state perceived most of the services under NHIA to be of moderate quality except consultative care services which female teachers perceived to be of high quality. There was no significant difference in the perception of quality between male and female teachers for services under NHIA. The implications of the study were highlighted and recommendations were made accordingly.

Introduction

Health insurance is a system for financing of medical expenses by means of contributions or taxes paid into a common fund to pay for all or part of health services specified in an insurance policy or law. The key elements common to most health insurance plans are advance payment of premiums or taxes, pooling of funds, and eligibility for benefits on the basis of contributions or employment. Health insurance may apply to a limited or comprehensive range of medical services and may provide for full or partial payment of the costs of specific services (Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2022). The benefits may consist of the right to certain medical services or reimbursement to the insured for specified medical costs. Some types of health insurance may also include income benefits for working time lost because of sickness (i.e., disability leave) or parental leave (Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2022).

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In Nigeria, National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) formerly known as the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS), is a social health insurance programme designed by the Nigerian government to complement sources of financing the health sector and to improve access to health care for the majority of Nigerians.

The Nigeria government established the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) under decree 35 of the 1999 constitution, however, the scheme did not become operational until about 6 years later on the 6 June, 2005 when it was officially launched and commencement of services to enrollees started in September of the same year (Obalum *et al*, 2012). Members who are enrolled in this scheme get to enjoy several benefits and services such as: Out-patient care, including necessary consumables; Prescribed drugs, pharmaceutical care and diagnostic tests- as contained in the National Essential Drug List and Diagnostic Test List; Maternity care for up to four (4) live births for every insured contributor/couple in the Formal Sector Programme; Preventive care, including immunization as it applies to the National Programme on Immunization, health education, family planning, antenatal and post-natal care; Consultation with specialist such as physicians, pediatricians, obstetricians, gynecologists, general surgeons, orthopedic surgeons, ear nose and throat (ENT) surgeons, dental surgeons, radiologists, psychiatrists, ophthalmologists, physiotherapists; Hospital care in a standard ward for a stay limited to a cumulative 15 days per year in non military Hospitals and no limit in Military Hospitals. The primary provider shall pay per diem for the bed space for a total of 15 days cumulative per year. Thereafter, the beneficiary and/or the employer Pay; Eye examination and care excluding provision of spectacles and contact lenses; a range of prostheses limited to artificial limbs produced in Nigeria; Preventive dental care and pain relief including consultation, dental health education, amalgam filling, and simple extraction. Teachers are one of the beneficiaries of NHIA due to the work schedule in terms of taking care of the school children and also a teacher being absent in class or school would disorganize the class and students been taught by such teacher. In order to avoid not being able to afford the cost of his or her health requirements and also because of the various benefits of NHIA, which prevents absence of teachers in their field of work, which would affect the students and also disrupt academic activities, there is need evaluate he services of NHIA as it is provided for themselves or for their family members. In order to determine whether NHIA is achieving their aims and objectives there is need to also evaluate their services for future modifications.

Evaluation means the process of judging or calculating the quality, importance, amount, or value of something including the services of the NHIA (Cambridge dictionary, 2023). The evaluation would be done bearing in mind their stated objectives as it concerns the teacher's welfare. Some many variables might determine the opinion of the teachers during evaluation these includes; gender, marital status, and designation of the teachers but this study will consider only gender. Most teachers are reluctant to use health care services under NHIA because these healthcare

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services are usually provided by government hospitals which are sometimes perceived to offer low quality healthcare services. Some healthcare services are perceived to be better rendered by private hospitals that are not under the NHIA. This is the reason why the researcher wants to evaluate the quality of service under the National Health insurance Authority from the perception of Unity school teachers in Anambra State.

Purpose of the study

The main aim of the study is to evaluate the quality of services by NHIA as perceived by Unity school teachers in Anambra State specifically:

1. To evaluate the quality of pharmaceutical care services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) as perceived by male and female teachers.
2. To evaluate the quality of diagnostic tests services under the NHIA as perceived by male and female teachers.
3. To evaluate the quality of outpatient care services under the NHIA as perceived by male and female teachers.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the quality of pharmaceutical care services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) as perceived by male and female teachers?
2. What is the quality of diagnostic tests services under the NHIA as perceived by male and female teachers?
3. What is the quality of outpatient care services under the NHIA as perceived by male and female teachers?

Hypothesis

The following null research hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the quality of pharmaceutical care services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) as perceived by male and female teachers.
2. There is no significant difference in the quality of diagnostic tests services under the NHIA as perceived by male and female teachers.
3. There is no significant difference in the quality of outpatient care services under the NHIA as perceived by male and female teachers.

Methods

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The design used in this study was a descriptive survey research design. The area of study was Anambra state. The samples of the study consist of 351 unity school teachers in Anambra state. The instrument for data collection was a researcher developed instrument in the form of a structured Questionnaire. The title of the questionnaire is “Quality of Health Care Services by National Health Insurance Authority Evaluation Questionnaire (QHCSNHIAEQ)”. the Reliability was done using Test-Test and Pearson’s Correlation which produced results for the following clusters: Pharmaceutical Care Services at 0.834, Diagnostic Care Services at 0.886, Outpatient Care Services at 0.860.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Research Questions One

What is the quality of pharmaceutical care services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) as perceived by male and female teachers?

Table 1

Mean Ratings of Male and Female Teachers on the Quality of Pharmaceutical Care Services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA)

Source of Variation	Mean	SD	Remark
Male (n=178)	2.82	0.40	Moderate Quality
Female (n=151)	2.86	0.49	Moderate Quality

The results presented in Table 1 shows the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the quality of pharmaceutical care services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA). The mean rating for the male teachers was 2.82 while that of the female teachers was 2.86. These values suggest that both male and female teachers perceived the quality of the pharmaceutical care services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) as moderate.

4.2 Research Questions Two

What is the quality of diagnostic tests services under the NHIA as perceived by male and female teachers?

Table 2

Mean Ratings of Male and Female Teachers on the Quality of Diagnostic Tests Services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA)

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Source of Variation	Mean	SD	Remark
Male (n=178)	3.01	0.35	Moderate Quality
Female (n=151)	2.96	0.38	Moderate Quality

The result displayed in Table 2 shows that the male teachers' mean rating of the quality of diagnostic tests under NHIA was 3.01, and the mean rating by the female teachers was 2.96. These mean ratings indicate that both male and female teachers perceived the quality of the diagnostic tests under NHIA as moderate. However, the male teachers had slightly higher mean rating than the female teachers as shown by the mean difference of 0.05.

4.3 Research Questions Three

What is the quality of outpatient care services under the NHIA as perceived by male and female teachers?

Table 3:

Mean Ratings of Male and Female Teachers on the Quality of Outpatient Care Services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA)

Source of Variation	Mean	SD	Remark
Male (n=178)	2.74	0.52	Moderate Quality
Female (n=151)	2.90	0.65	Moderate Quality

As shown in Table 3, the mean rating of the quality of outpatient care services by the male teachers was 2.74 while that of the female teachers was 2.90. This shows a mean difference of 0.16. Although the mean rating of the female teachers was slightly higher than the mean rating of the male teachers, both groups perceived the quality of the outpatient care services as moderate.

Hypothesis One

There will be no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the quality of pharmaceutical care services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA).

Table 4 : *T-test Analysis on Mean Ratings of Male and Female Teachers on the Quality of Pharmaceutical Care Services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA)*

Source of variation	N	Mean	SD	df	T	p-value	Remark
Male	178	2.82	0.40				
Female	151	2.86	0.49	327	-0.82	0.42	Not Significant

The results of the independent samples t-test displayed in Table 6 shows that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers regarding the quality of pharmaceutical care services under National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA), $t(327) = -0.82$, $p = 0.42$. Since the p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Hypothesis Two

There will be no significant difference in the quality of diagnostic tests services under the NHIA as perceived by male and female teachers.

Table 5: *T-test Analysis on Mean Ratings of Male and Female Teachers on the Quality of Diagnostic Tests Services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA)*

Source of variation	N	Mean	SD	df	T	P-value	Remark
Male	178	3.01	0.35				
Female	151	2.96	0.38	327	1.36	0.17	Not Significant

The results of the independent samples t-test displayed in Table 7 shows that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers regarding the quality of diagnostic tests services under National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA), $t(327) = 1.36$, $p = 0.17$. Since the p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Hypothesis Three

There will be no significant difference in the quality of outpatient care services under the NHIA as perceived by male and female teachers.

Table 6: *T-test Analysis on Mean Ratings of Male and Female Teachers on the Quality of Outpatient Care Services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA)*

Source of variation	N	Mean	SD	df	T	P-value	Remark
Male	178	2.74	0.52				
Female	151	2.90	0.65	327	-1.01	0.31	Not Significant

The t-test result displayed in Table 8 indicates that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the quality of outpatient care services under National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA), $t(327) = -1.01$, $p = 0.31$. Since the p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Discussion of findings

The quality of pharmaceutical care services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) as perceived by male and female teachers.

The results presented in Table 1 shows the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the quality of pharmaceutical care services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA). The mean rating for the male teachers was 2.82 while that of the female teachers was 2.86. These values suggest that both male and female teachers perceived the quality of the pharmaceutical care services under the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) as moderate.

This supports a study by Uguru *et al* (2024) which showed that respondents across all the socio-economic groups reported that the NHIA had marginally improved access to medicine over the years. However, it was also observed that most of the staff in NHIA-accredited facilities were not adequately trained on the scheme's requirements and that most times, essential drugs were not readily available at the accredited facilities. The study findings also revealed that although the NHIS has successfully expanded access to medicines, there remain several challenges to its effective implementation and sustainability.

The quality of diagnostic tests services under the NHIA as perceived by male and female teachers.

The result displayed in Table 2 shows that the male teachers' mean rating of the quality of diagnostic tests under NHIA was 3.01, and the mean rating by the female teachers was 2.96. These mean ratings indicate that both male and female teachers perceived the quality of the diagnostic tests under NHIA as moderate.

This aligns with a study by Nwanaji-Enwerem *et al* (2022) where they opined that the beneficiaries of the NHIS now NHIA are moderately satisfied with the scheme. They consider it an improvement from being uninsured, but believe that the scheme can be considerably improved.

The quality of outpatient care services under the NHIA as perceived by male and female teachers.

As shown in Table 3, the mean rating of the quality of outpatient care services by the male teachers was 2.74 while that of the female teachers was 2.90. This shows a mean difference of 0.16. Although the mean rating of the female teachers was slightly higher than the mean rating of the male teachers, both groups perceived the quality of the outpatient care services as moderate.

A study by Mkperedem *et al* (2023) claims that the quality of medical personnel attitudes during outpatient care has a significant relationship with enrollees' perception. The implication is that perception may be altered depending on the attitude displayed upon the next visit to the same or a different hospital. Following the sharp contrast between the questionnaire reports and the IDI, the research further concludes that enrollees' perception is sharpened by their experience or the experience of others witnessed or heard.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, the following conclusions were made;

Both male and female teachers of unity schools rated the quality of pharmaceutical care services under NHIA as moderate in standard. There wasn't much of a difference in the perception of the two groups. Both male and female teachers perceived the quality of the diagnostic tests under NHIA as moderate in quality. Although the mean rating of the female teachers was slightly higher than the mean rating of the male teachers, both groups perceived the quality of the outpatient care services as moderate.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and the implications, the following recommendations were made:

1. More funding should go into pharmaceutical care services like supply of high quality medicines, employment and training of more pharmacists and provision of bigger pharmacies in other to reduce waiting times.
2. There should be improved standardisation of facilities used in diagnostic tests. Also, provision of more laboratories would improve the perception of quality.
3. More improvements in ambulatory services are necessary. More ambulances should be provided and properly maintained for emergencies.

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